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INDEX

SECTION 1: OBJECTIVE OF THE WORK	3
SECTION 2: MECHANICAL MIXING	3
SECTION 3: FREEZE GRANULATION	6
SECTION 4: SPRAY GRANULATION	7
SECTION 5: SPRAY DRYING	10
SECTION 6: COPRECIPITATION	12
SECTION 7: SOL-GEL SYNTHESIS	14
SECTION 8: IMPREGNATION	15
SECTION 9: PREPARED SAMPLES	17
BIBLIOGRAPHY	24

SECTION 1: OBJECTIVE OF THE WORK

To couple a CLC reactor with a gas turbine, pressurized conditions are needed in the reactors and conditions of high temperature. What are the oxygen carriers (OCs) preparation methods which can better perform in these conditions? Obviously a great part is played by the materials themselves, which will be analyzed in a specific database, but also the preparation method can play a significant role. As per literature review [1] we see again that the classification of the OCs is made on the base of the metal type, which is contained in them. But what is the role of the preparation technique? To analyze this aspect the following workpackage has collected both experimental and literature data, during the Marie Curie IF project GTCLC-NEG. The main method taken into account for the preparation of the oxygen carriers are: mechanical mixing, spray drying, granulation, impregnation, solgel, coprecipitation, flash combustion. Solgel, coprecipitation and flash combustion are not used in the Instituto de Carboquímica (CSIC). Particular attention has to be put on the scalability of the process if we want the CLC technology to be performed at the scale and capacity of the targeted gas turbine plants, which is about 12-16 MWe. Main methods have been taken from [2].

SECTION 2: Mechanical Mixing

The mechanical mixing method is suitable for both ores and synthetic materials. Those materials can be mixed after decreasing their size to around 100–300 μm to make them suitable for fluidized bed operation. In literature together with ilmenite and hematite [3-12] also calcined bauxite waste and iron oxide scales from the steel industry have also been examined, yielding high crushing strengths of resp. 2.8–4.3 N [7, 13-15] and up to 8.3 N [16].

When several materials must be combined (e.g., one support material and an active phase), the mechanical mixing/extrusion method is frequently used. A simple flowchart of this process is included in Figure 1. First, the raw materials are reduced in size for enabling enough mixing and achieving a sufficiently homogeneous microstructure in the final particle. Afterward, suitable solvents are added (usually water), and the materials

are then mixed into a paste. Some additives may be added to enable pore formation and/or sufficient stabilization of the paste before it is extruded.

In particular at the Instituto de Carboquímica (CSIC) a pelletizer is used, in which the powder is charged. The mixtures are pelletized by pressure in a hydraulic press at 165 bar during 60 seconds. Cylindrical pellets are so obtained of about 1 cm in diameter and 3 cm in length see figure 2. Once produced the pellets are then calcinated, see figure 2.

The resulting extrudates are then dried, before crushing them into particles with sizes suitable for fluidization. Before or after size reduction, a post-heat-treatment is executed to sufficiently strengthen the particles to improve their longevity. While the control on the nanoscale is limited, the intermixing of the grains can be controlled to some extent, and the heat treatment can provide some control over the remaining porosity and strength of the oxygen carriers.

Figure 1. Mechanical Mixing Process [17]

Mechanical mixing yields fluidizable particles without a very costly procedure and is, therefore, commonly used. However, the flowability of the particles can be quite low due to their irregular morphology that might also affect their mechanical performance (especially resistance to attrition during the first hours of operation due to rounding effects [4]).

Figure 2: Hydraulic press for the production of pelletized oxygen carriers

SECTION 3: Freeze granulation

Even though this method is not performed in the Instituto de Carboquímica laboratories it is explained to have a complete idea of the possible available methods. Freeze granulation is another method starting from solid raw materials, with little control on the spray nozzle, which was previously used in small-scale oxygen carrier development. In this process, which is schematically displayed in Figure 3, a fine metal oxide powder is usually combined with the necessary dispersing agents and water into a slurry.

Figure 3: Freeze granulation [17]

This slurry is then homogenized by ball milling, and a binder is added for providing sufficient strength during granulation and handling before sintering. Spherical particles are then produced by pumping the water-based slurry through a spray nozzle, where passing atomizing air gives energy for the formation of drops. These drops of slurry are then sprayed into liquid nitrogen, where they instantly freeze to the solid state. The frozen water inside these drops is then removed by sublimation in a freeze-dryer, and the remaining porous particles are sintered at different temperatures to achieve sufficient crushing strength.

A big advantage of the freeze granulation technique is the large porosity, which can be generated inside the particles. This porosity can facilitate gas diffusion during the chemical looping processes to achieve enough reactivity. The drawback of particles with very high porosity, however, is their low mechanical strength. Sintering for times long enough at sufficiently high temperatures can decrease generating engineered oxygen carriers the oxygen carrier porosity and thus mitigate the low strength of the particles. Another disadvantage of utilizing the freeze granulation technique is the high cost related to the use of liquid nitrogen. Freeze granulation is, therefore, only suitable for very small-scale production, mainly during particle screening, as in [18].

SECTION 4: Spray Granulation

The spray granulation process converts a water-containing solution, paste or suspension or a melt into a granule. The granulation and the drying processes take place at the same time.

The process mechanism is shown in figure 4. The granules can be calcinated once the preparation is finished.

The facilities used for spray granulation at the Instituto de Carboquímica (CSIC) are shown in figure 5.

Figure 4: Spray drying mechanism [19]

Figure 5: Spray granulator in a spouted bed system (ProCell LabSystem, Glatt, at the Laboratories of the Instituto de Carboquímica in Zaragoza, Spain

Figure 6: Spray Granulator display (left) and final product (right)

Another granulator used in the laboratories of the Instituto de Carboquímica is shown in figure 7.

Figure 7: Granulator used at the laboratories of the Instituto de Carboquímica

The process to produce mixed iron and manganese oxygen carriers is shown in figure 8.

Figure 8: Mixed iron-manganese Oxygen carriers preparation

SECTION 5: Spray-Drying

Even though this method is not performed in the Instituto de Carboquímica laboratories it is explained to have a complete idea of the possible available methods. An alternative technique, which is quite similar to freeze granulation and which is much more viable on an industrial scale, is spray-drying. This technique is, therefore, frequently used for generating engineered oxygen carriers throughout the past decades. The main advantages of using spray-drying are the following:

- Homogeneous microstructure
- Scalable process
- Relatively low cost compared to more advanced techniques
- Free-flowing oxygen carriers
- Suitable particle sizes and porosities
- Continuous process

- No side products generated.

The process, (see Figure 9, for a general flowsheet), consists of making a suitable suspension/slurry from the raw materials, a solvent (generally water), and suitable additives for improving suspension stability and viscosity, much like in freeze granulation. The metal oxygen particles inside this suspension should be sufficiently reduced in size and homogenized before the suspension is introduced in the spray-dryer for achieving a homogeneous and fine microstructure. The suspension is then sprayed into droplets by a nozzle in a hot air stream in the spray-dryer, where spherical particles are generated, and the water is immediately removed. These spray-dried particles are then classified by size, and the suitable fraction (depending on the particle density and the design of the fluidized bed reactors) is then calcined and heat-treated for achieving sufficient mechanical properties during a post-treatment, which is used for strengthening the particles for use in fluidized bed technology.

Figure 9: A simple flow chart of the spray drying process (a) and of the coprecipitation process (b) [17]

Although spray-drying is industrially feasible for oxygen carrier production and thus commonly used when large amounts of oxygen carriers are needed for pilot-scale tests, the control on the nanoscale is generally very limited. This, in general, leads to lower activity, when compared to the previously described methods.

SECTION 6: Coprecipitation

Even though this method is not performed in the Instituto de Carboquímica laboratories it is explained to have a complete idea of the possible available methods. Coprecipitation is one of the synthesis techniques where powders are produced from metal salts. With this method, optimal control of the composition at the nanoscale can be achieved. In general (see Figure 10), metal nitrates or chlorides are dissolved in deionized water, and pH-adjusting agents, such as $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{CO}_3$, NH_4OH , or urea, are added until a certain pH is reached. The solubility of the components in the solution decreases, and certain precipitates are generated. During precipitation, several parameters may affect the coprecipitation process (e.g., stirring, temperature, time) and the produced precipitates. These precipitates are then dried (after a possible washing step) and calcined before post-processing. This post-processing may include heat treatment for achieving necessary solid-state reactions and granulation and shaping techniques.

The coprecipitation method starts with very pure chemicals, and a lot of waste is generated during the process. These aspects make coprecipitation more expensive compared to other synthesis techniques. Although the process can be up-scaled, and the morphology, composition, and microstructure of the final particles can be designed to an extensive degree, the cost of the process is generally too high for industrial-scale chemical looping [20]. Due to the excellent control on the nanoscale, this method is most often applied when synthesizing novel OC materials, displaying an excellent chemical performance (conversion and selectivity).

Figure 10: Co-precipitation method [21, 22]

SECTION 7: Sol-Gel Synthesis

Even though this method is not performed in the Instituto de Carboquímica laboratories it is explained to have a complete idea of the possible available methods. Sol-gel synthesis, similarly to coprecipitation, also involves the use of metal salts. Instead of changing the pH of a solution yielding precipitates, a sol is created, which is a colloidal suspension changing the pH of a solution yielding precipitates, a sol is created, which is a colloidal suspension that that can act as a precursor for the formation of an integrated network (gel). The metal salts that are used used can range from conventional metal salts, such as chlorides, to metal alkoxides. These salts undergo polycondensation and hydrolysis reactions to form the colloid and, depending on the process conditions and the chemicals used, very porous to dense materials, as well as uniformly sized particles, can be generated. The excellent control on the nanoscale can also significantly improve the OC properties.

A general flowchart used in the synthesis of powders for oxygen carriers by the sol-gel method is included in Figure 11.

Figure 11: A simple flowchart of the sol-gel process [17]

Sol-gel synthesis is very complex, and as it is less suitable to produce for large scale chemical looping processes due to its complexity and high cost, therefore, we will not go into detail. The review paper of Danks et al. gives more information about the different can be used and the parameters that can be tuned in the different sol-gel processes [23], which might also be applicable for oxygen carrier material synthesis.

SECTION 8: Impregnation

Impregnation is another synthesis method suitable for large-scale oxygen carrier production. The main difference with the other methods is the fact that it can only be used to activate a suitable support material by increasing the amount of active phase or adding a certain component that improves the OC performance. It should, therefore, be described more as an activation method, rather than a synthesis method. A flow chart is included in Figure 12. There are generally two different impregnation methods, which can be differentiated by the amount of solvent used in the process. During the incipient wetness impregnation method, the porous substrates are first dried, followed by the filling of only the pores with metal-salt solutions (due to the capillary effect). In the wet impregnation method, the porous (or even non-porous) substrates are immersed in excess of metal salt solution. In both methods, the next step includes the evaporation of the solvent by a drying step. During this drying step, the salt solution becomes supersaturated, resulting in precipitation of metal salts in the pores and on the surface of the substrate. Afterward, these precipitates are converted to oxides during a suitably designed calcination step.

One drawback of impregnation is the limited loading of the support per impregnation step. This can be overcome by executing several impregnation steps on the same material or by increasing the solubility of the materials that are to be deposited. Impregnation, is also commonly used when improving the reactivity of certain ores for use in CLC, e.g. by impregnating them with Cu oxides.

Figure 12: A simple flowchart for the impregnation process [17]

Preparation of the sample Fe₂₀γAl at ICB-CSIC

Fe₂₀ was prepared by impregnation using commercial γ -Al₂O₃ (Puralox NWA-155, Sasol Germany GmbH) particles of 0.1–0.32 mm, with density of 1.3 g/cm³ and porosity of 55.4% as support.

The oxygen carrier was prepared impregnating the support heated at 80 °C in a planetary mixer with a saturated iron nitrate solution [Fe(NO₃)₃·9H₂O] at 60 - 80 °C (3.8 M). This solution was slowly added to the alumina particles stirring at hot temperature (80 °C). The material resulting from the first impregnation was calcined at 550 °C in air atmosphere for 30 min to decompose the impregnated metal nitrate into the metal oxide. Finally, after the second impregnation, the oxygen carrier was sintered in a furnace at 950 °C for 1 h.

SECTION 9: Prepared Samples

The samples prepared are the following:

1. Fe₂₀γAl
2. Ni₁₈αAl
3. Ilmenite
4. Tierga ore
5. Iron-Manganese-Titanium based oxygen carriers (Mn₂₈FeTi₇, Mn₅₅FeTi₇, Mn₆₆FeTi₇, Mn₈₇FeTi₇), according to [24-26]
6. MnTi mixtures, according to [27]

We propose one page for each final sample realized.

Sample name: Fe₂₀γAl

Sample number: 1

Preparation method: Impregnation

Sample picture:

Sample name: Ni18 α Al

Sample number: 2

Preparation method: Impregnation

Sample picture:

Sample name: Ilmenite

Sample number: 3

Preparation method: Mechanical mixing

Sample picture:

Sample name: Tierga ore

Sample number: 4

Preparation method: Mechanical mixing

Sample picture:

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Sample name: Iron-Manganese-Titanium based oxygen carriers

Sample number: 5

Preparation method: Mechanical mixing

Sample picture:

Sample name: Managanes-Iron Oxygen carriers

Sample number: 6

Preparation method: Mechanical mixing

Sample picture:

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